

Mapping Research Topics on Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to find out a map of research developments around Risk Management in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions with a bibliometric study of VOSviewer and a literature review study. The research was conducted over a period of 17 years from 2006 to 2022 by conducting a search through the Garuda website (Garba Referral Digital) said the key to Risk Management. And there were 231 research articles. The search result articles were then analyzed descriptively, inputted, analyzed with VOSviewer and literature review studies to find out visualizations mapping the development of research topics and subjects around Risk Management. The results showed that the number of publications around Risk Management increased significantly every year. Then, based on the results of mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research around Risk Management is divided into 9 clusters. Meanwhile, based on the review of the literature review, there are 4 main themes around Risk Management in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Risk Management, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

Risk management is the process of controlling the possibility of risks arising in the future. Companies can detect and recognize any risks that have the potential to hinder company goals through implementing good risk management. Good risk management will be able to control company risks well in the future. This is because risk management is a science that discusses how an organization applies measures to identify various existing problems, using a comprehensive and systematic management approach.

Sharia banking is part of financial institutions that use sharia principles in their activities and avoid usury. The application of sharia principles is based on sharia compliance. In practice, sharia compliance is checked by the Sharia Supervisory Board (DPS). DPS is selected and appointed by the National Sharia Council (DSN) to supervise the activities of financial institutions in order to ensure that they comply with the rules and principles of Islamic sharia, the fatwa of DPS regulations is binding on these Islamic financial institutions.

Risks in Islamic banks arise because of the large number of cases in Islamic banks. It cannot be denied that Islamic banks are financial service intermediary institutions (intermediary) is responsible for collecting funds from the community and channeling them back to the community in the form of financing. Financing is called that because sharia banks provide funds to meet the needs of customers who need and are entitled to receive them. Therefore, the higher the level of financing of a bank, the higher the level of risk. So the role of risk management is needed in reducing risks that arise in the future.

Every year, the number of scientific publications on Risk Management in Financial Institutions continues to increase. On the Garuda Digital Referral (Garuda) website, there are 231 studies on Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional

Financial Institutions until 2022. This shows that researchers are very interested in research on Risk Management. The accumulation of opportunities for uncertain events to occur that affect project goals and objectives.

The aim of this research is to determine the development of research on risk management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions over a period of 17 years (2006 - 2022) using the VOS viewer bibliometric method and literature review studies.

Literature Review

Risk management is a series of methodologies and procedures that aim to identify, measure, monitor and control risks arising from sharia bank operational activities (PBI No 11/25/PBI/2009). Risk management is a concept that designs the implementation of procedures that are useful in managing business risks so that they can be minimized. There are 10 types of risk in banking, including credit, market, liquidity, operational, legal, reputation, strategic, compliance, returns and investment risks. However, credit and liquidity risks are the most basic risks and are most frequently faced by the banking sector.

The Qur'an in Surah Al-Hasyr verse 18, which means: "O you who believe, fear Allah and let each person pay attention to what he has done for tomorrow and fear Allah. Indeed, Allah is All-Knowing of what you do." This paragraph emphasizes the importance of implementing risk management for sharia financial institutions, because risk is always present in every activity and the future is difficult to predict and there is always uncertainty that creates risk. Implementation of risk management is allowed to properly prepare the things that will be done to minimize risks that occur in the future. Human resources in sharia financial institutions must have intuition about things that have the potential to pose a threat to financial institutions and must be able to know, analyze and study risks that are considered to have the potential to be detrimental in the future.

Bibliometric analysis (bibliometrics) is also called scientometrics which is part of the research evaluation methodology, and from the various literature that has been produced, it is possible to carry out bibliometric analysis using its own method. The bibliometric method is a method of measuring literature using a statistical approach that includes the application of quantitative analysis.

VOSviewer is software used to create, explore, and visualize metadata network maps. VOSviewer has two main functions: (1) creates a bibliometric map based on a metadata network, which can create a network of scientific publications, journals, researchers, institutions, countries, and keywords that are already available or not yet available; and (2) visualizing and exploring bibliometric maps. VOSviewer provides three forms of visualization, namely network visualization, overlay, and density.

Literature review is searching and researching the literature by reading various books, journals and other publications related to the research topic, to produce writing about a particular topic or issue. The literature review was carried out with the awareness that knowledge continues to increase and is accumulative.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The research object is Risk Management. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles on Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Risk Management " and " Risk Management " within the entire year (2006 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

The findings of this research are the number of articles published on the Garuda website during the period 2006 - 2022. Based on data obtained from research on the Garuda website, there are 231 articles related to risk management, especially those containing discussion of sharia risk, from accredited national journals. In fact, in 2022, there were 46 articles published. So, the average scientific publication related to Risk Management per year is around 13 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Risk Management by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2006	1	2015	21	2019	25
2011	4	2016	8	2020	19
2012	5	2017	23	2021	29
2013	6	2018	28	2022	46
2014	16				
Total 231					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In Table 2, there are the 10 affiliated institutions that publish the most research articles on Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions. The scientific journal Economics and Banking, Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta is the largest journal publishing institution that publishes results on Risk Management with a total of 9 articles published.

Table 2. Affiliates/Institutions publishing scientific journals about Risk Management

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, Journal of Jurish-Diction, Airlangga University	9
MASHARIFAL SYARIAH: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Muhammadiyah University Surabaya	8
Accounting Journal, Diponegoro University	7

Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics (ITB AAS Indonesia Surakarta), FEB Student Scientific Journal, Journal of Management Applications (Brawijaya University)	6
WADIAH Journal, IAIN Kediri	5
MASLAHAH: Journal of Islamic Law and Sharia Banking, Islamic University "45" Bekasi, Journal of Business Economics and Accounting (STIE Perbanas), Journal of Motivation in Business and Economics, FALAH: Journal of Sharia Economics, Journal of Accounting and Finance Review (Muhammadiyah University of Malang)	4
Journal of Accounting Scientific Work, UNTAN (KIAFE), Journal of Sharia Economics, Accounting and Banking (Jeskape), IAIN Lhokseumawe	3

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 3, the most productive researchers are shown, namely: Adityawarman from Diponegoro University Semarang, who wrote 5 articles.

Table 3. Researchers on Risk Management

Researcher	Number of Publications
Adityawarman (Diponegoro University)	5
Agustina Djoko (NU University Surabaya), Akbar, Anwar (NU University Surabaya), Usanti, Trisadini Prasastinah (Yarsi University), Hendrianto, Ika Gustin (IAIN Curup)	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Article search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Risk Management

conventional bank, conventional banking, covid, determinant, dimension, empirical evidence, equity, factors.

- Cluster 6. Light Blue consists of 10 topic items, namely: asset ratio, Indonesian sharia bank, bi rate, bjb syariah, bsi, debt, december, der, exchange rate, external factor, factor, firm, gdp.
- Cluster 7. Orange consists of 6 topic items, namely: causal relationship, credit, credit risk, ijarah, mudarabah, murabahah.
- Cluster 8. Black consists of 4 topic items, namely: bank risk, fees, income, magnitude.
- Cluster 9. Light Purple consists of 2 topic items, namely: Malaysia, profit distribution management.

Literature Review Study regarding Legal Basis, Scope, Policies, Procedures and Determination of Risk Management Limits in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

First, the legal basis. The findings in this research topic are: (1) Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 13/23/2011; (2) Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 11/25/2009 amendment Number 5/8/2003; (3) Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 18/POJK.03/2016; (4) Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 65/POJK.03/2016; (5) Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 13/POJK.03/2015; (6) Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 23/POJK.03/2018; and (7) Islamic Financial Services Board/IFSB.

Second, the scope of risk. The findings in this research topic are: (1) credit risk; (2) market risk; (3) liquidity risk; (4) operational risk; (5) compliance risk; (6) legal risks; (7) reputation risk; (8) strategic risk; (9) risk of returns and investment in Sharia Commercial Banks; and (10) risks 1, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8 apply to Rural Banks/BPR and BPRS for those with core capital of fifty billion rupiah.

Third, risk management policy. The findings in this research topic are: (1) risk determination, measurement methods, limits, tolerances, rating assessments, contingency plans in crisis situations, and internal control systems; and (2) prepared at least once a year.

Fourth, risk management procedures. The findings in this research topic are: (1) determining procedures is based on the level of bank risk to be taken; and (2) accountability of those giving policy authority, reviewing and documenting procedures in writing, complete and easy, and periodically at least once a year.

Fifth, setting risk limits. The findings in this research topic are: (1) determining adequate and regular risk limits; and (2) its coverage, either overall, per risk type or per specific operational activity.

Literature Review Study regarding Factors that Influence Risk Management Disclosures in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

First, the Board of Directors. The findings in this research topic are: (1) the authority and responsibility of the Board of Directors regarding preparation, strategy, implementation, evaluation, transaction decisions, cultural development, increasing HR competency (through regular training and education programs), ensuring functions, determining methodology, and application of information systems to risk management policies; and (2) The Board of Directors properly understands the risks associated with all bank operational activities (related to products, services, other activities) and is able to take the necessary policies in accordance with the bank's risk profile.

Second, the Board of Commissioners. The findings in this research topic are: the authority and responsibility of the Board of Commissioners regarding approval,

policy evaluation and evaluation of the Board of Directors' accountability which is carried out at least once a year.

Third, the Sharia Supervisory Board at Sharia Financial Institutions. The findings in this research topic are: the authority and responsibility of the Sharia Supervisory Board regarding policy evaluation (carried out at least once a year) and evaluation of the accountability of the Board of Directors according to sharia principles (carried out at least once a quarter).

Literature Review Study regarding Identification, Measurement, Monitoring, Control and Risk Management Information Systems in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

First, the risk identification system. The findings in this research topic are: (1) analyzing the risk characteristics of each operational activity and Bank product on a regular basis at least once a quarter; (2) anti-money laundering/TPPU and terrorism financing programs including risk identification coverage; and (3) use of a quantitative or qualitative approach.

Second, the risk measurement system. The findings in this research topic are that there is a periodic evaluation and improvement of the system for every business activity, transaction, product, which can affect the Bank's financial condition.

Third, a risk monitoring system. The findings in this research topic are the evaluation and improvement of the reporting process for product innovation, information technology, information systems and material bank business activities.

Fourth, risk control system. The findings in this research topic are: (1) there is prevention of dangers that will disrupt the Bank's business continuity and are in accordance with sharia principles; and (2) risk control can be implemented by increasing capital, risk mitigation and hedging.

Fifth, risk management information system. The findings in this research topic are reports and information regarding exposure, compliance, procedures, limit determination and the realization of risk management implementation which are submitted periodically to the Board of Directors using Conventional Commercial Bank (BUK) information system technology.

Sixth, internal control system. The findings in this research topic are: (1) suitability to the type and level of risk of the Bank's business activities; and (2) determining authority, responsibility, reporting lines between work units, organizational structure, financial reports, operational activities, adequacy of procedures, adequate review, documentation, regular verification of risk management policies.

Literature Review Study regarding Organization, Function, Profile Reporting and Administrative Sanctions for Delay in Risk Management Reporting in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

First, the risk management committee. The findings in this research topic are: (1) consisting of the Compliance Director and executive officers; (2) authority and responsibility includes the preparation of policies, guidelines, strategies, improvements, business decisions regarding the implementation of risk management, which are then given to the President Director as a recommendation; (3) committee members consist of permanent and non-permanent members, according to company needs; and (4) BPR/BPRS which have core capital of less than eighty billion rupiah are not required to form a risk management committee, but are required to appoint at least 1 Executive Officer who is responsible for risk management.

Second, the risk management work unit. The findings in this research topic are: (1) authority and responsibility includes monitoring strategy implementation, risk positions, periodic reviews, proposals for new activities/products, evaluation of

risk measurements, recommendations to operational work units, preparation and reporting of risk profiles, then all of this is conveyed to the President Director/Board of Directors and the Risk Management Committee; and (2) BPR/BPRS which have core capital of less than eighty billion rupiah are not required to form a risk management work unit.

Third, risk profile reporting. The findings in this research topic are: (1) Banks are required to report the risk profile of their business activities quarterly (March, June, September, December) or when the report is requested by/to the Financial Services Authority (OJK) whose address is the Sharia Banking Department or Office Regional OJK; (2) this reporting functions to assess the Bank's soundness level in accordance with OJK regulations; (3) Banks must report data and information regarding the implementation of risk management within the bank and carry out assessments thereof; and (4) performance disclosure includes at least risk management performance and policy direction attached to the Bank's annual published report, in accordance with POJK.

Fourth, administrative sanctions. The findings in this research topic are: (1) late submission of reports will result in a fine of one million rupiah per day per report; (2) failure to submit reports will result in a fine of fifty million rupiah per report; (3) submitting incomplete reports and not attaching material documents and information will result in a fine of fifty million rupiah; and (4) other administrative sanctions, including written warnings, suspension of certain business activities, and inclusion of a list of failures by related parties regarding fit and proper competency.

Literature Review Study regarding the Implementation of Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

The application of risk management to Financial Institutions and their products includes: (1) the ALMA (Asset and Liabilities Management) approach; (2) Good Corporate Governance (GCG); (3) Basel Accord I/II/III approach; (4) disbursement of traveller's checks to prevent criminal acts; (5) Stock Based & Flow Based approach; (6) facing Cyber Security threats; (7) digital era; (8) business ethics; (9) during the Covid-19 pandemic; (10) community business transactions; (11) implementation of the National Institute of Standards and Technology/NIST & Indonesian Banking Architecture/API; (12) data mining applications; (13) Center for Risk Management Indonesia/CRMS; (14) based on Artificial Intelligence; (15) linkage program approach to executing Mudharabah contracts (16) hedging transactions; (17) minimizing the risk of bad credit/financing problems; (18) COBIT Framework 2019 approach; (19) minimizing Bank Guarantee product claims; (20) use of ISO 31000:2018; (21) use of the RiskIT Framework to reduce information technology risks; (22) preventing closed agreements/tying agreements in bancassurance cooperation activities; (23) granting credit without collateral/determining the suitability of collateral; (24) correlation of internal & external factors with company assets; (25) preventing cases of bank ATM skimming; (26) use of Bank Indonesia Fintech Office; (27) use of E-Banking/Mobile Banking/Internet Banking; (28) Micro Waqf Bank; (29) Sensitivity Gap formation; (30) pawn financing/gold installments, Home Ownership Credit/KPR, Mudharabah/profit sharing, Murabahah, Musyarakah Mutanaqishah, credit agreements, working capital, micro shop financing, Kafalah products, Natural Uncertainty Contracts/NUC.

Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Risk Management on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Risk management systems and policies in Financial Institutions affect several things, including: (1) profitability; (2) customer interest; (3) company value; (4) health level; (5) Net Interest Margin (NIM); (6) Non-Performing Loans (NPL); (7) Return on Assets (ROA); (8) bonus compensation; (9) customer satisfaction; investment interest;

(10) capital ratio; (11) flexibility; (12) company profits; (13) changes in initial share price; (14) financial performance; (15) employee performance; (16) efficiency; (17) stock price/profit; (18) organizational performance; (19) capital; (20) company image; (21) credit granting policy; and (22) Islamicity Performance Index.

Literature Review Study regarding Factors that Influence the Application and Level of Risk in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Factors that influence the implementation of risk management in financial institutions include: (1) human resources/HR; (2) company management policies; (3) office/infrastructure networks; (4) government regulations; (5) responsibility/commitment; (6) management ownership; (7) type of industry; (8) product diversification; (9) profitability; and (10) company age.

Meanwhile, factors that influence the level of risk in financial institutions include: (1) Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR; (2) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; (3) Good Corporate Governance/GCG; (4) Return On Assets/ROA; (5) Return On Equity/ROE; (6) Non Performing Financing/NPF; (7) Operational Expenses to Operational Financing (BOPO); (8) company size/Bank Size; (9) Gross Domestic Product (GDP); (10) Maqasid Sharia; (11) world oil prices; (12) exchange rate; (13) diversification of economic sector financing; (14) inflation; (15) public ownership; (16) leverage; (17) information technology; (18) governance; and (19) capital adequacy.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 2006 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 231 research articles.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Scientific Journal of Economics and Banking, Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta. The total number of publications is 9 research articles.
- The most productive researcher in publishing research results is Adityawarman from Diponegoro University, Semarang. The total number of publications is 5 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, research developments regarding Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 9 clusters. Cluster 1 consists of 36 topics, cluster 2 consists of 31 topics, cluster 3 consists of 25 topics, cluster 4 consists of 20 topics, cluster 5 consists of 14 topics, cluster 6 consists of 10 topics, cluster 7 consists of 6 topics, cluster 8 consists of 4 topics, cluster 9 consists of 2 topics.
- Based on the literature review, there are seven main research themes surrounding Risk Management in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) legal basis, scope, policy, procedures and determination of risk management limits; (2) factors that influence risk management disclosure; (3) identification, measurement, monitoring, control, information systems; (4) organization, function, profile reporting, administrative sanctions for late reporting; (5) implementation of risk management; (6) the influence of risk management; and (7) factors influencing implementation and level of risk.

is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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